

Recommended citation: Hockicko, P., & Tarjániová, G. (2018). Inventory of drop-out rate, interventions and conception in Physics during first year of study at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 856-863). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672718.

Inventory of drop-out rate, interventions and conception in Physics during the first year of study at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering

Peter Hockicko¹

Associate professor, Vice-dean for research
Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Žilina
Žilina, Slovakia
E-mail: hockicko@fyzika.uniza.sk

Gabriela Tarjániová

Assistant of professor
Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Žilina
Žilina, Slovakia
E-mail: tarjanyiova@fyzika.uniza.sk

Conference Key Areas: Innovative Teaching and Learning Methods, Engineering Skills, Educational and Organizational Development

Keywords: STEM education, drop-out rate, FCI test,

INTRODUCTION

The current situation at Slovak technical universities shows a decreasing trend in the number of students interested in studying STEM subjects. Also, the number of students who prematurely end in the first year of study because they are not able to study at university for a variety of reasons is quite large. Therefore, we joined the project readySTEMgo in which our university set the following goals:

University of Žilina fulfilled the following goals during the implementation of readySTEMgo project:

¹Corresponding Author
Peter Hockicko
hockicko@fyzika.uniza.sk

- to analyse the drop-out rate freshmen at the University of Žilina and try to decrease the number of drop-outs,
- to evaluate the effectiveness of our intervention tools.
(Some of them were the Summer Course of Physics organized before starting of the semester and interactive Physics lectures organized during Introduction to Physics (first semester) and Physics I (second semester).)
- to plan to learn from our project partners and try to implement their best practices at our university.

1 DROP-OUT RATE OF FRESHMEN

Our previous research revealed that about 30-50% of freshmen drop out during the first year of studying [1, 2].

Table 1. The drop-out rate in University of Žilina. The first number in table stands for the freshmen who drop out during their 1st year, the second number indicates the number of enrolled students.

	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17
Faculty of <i>Electrical Engineering</i>	134/412 = 33 %	134/310 = 43 %	110/235 = 47 %	56/233 = 24%
Faculty of <i>Civil Engineering</i>	116/246 = 47 %	62/126 = 46 %	59/109 = 54%	141/196 = 72%
Faculty of <i>Mechanical Engineering</i>	167/340 = 49 %	118/256 = 46 %	70/180 = 39 %	68/235 = 28%

One of the factors influencing the drop-out rate is low prior freshmen knowledge of mathematics and physics (based on internal discussion with students). Another one is their negative attitude towards STEM subjects [1]. Therefore, the question arose how to improve the knowledge of the low-achieving students. One of the possible solutions to this problem was to supplement the lack of freshmen knowledge at the beginning of their studies.

2 INTERVENTION TOOLS

Therefore, we offered our freshmen the pilot introductory summer course, which aim was to enhance the prior knowledge and to foster participants' awareness in most frequently used concepts from higher mathematics and physics as well as to develop their knowledge in calculus. We started with the courses at the beginning of the academic year 2015/16. The Summer Course, which is discussed in the article, was held before the start of the winter semester of the academic year 2016/2017 and it consisted of 20 lessons and lasted five days. The course was attended by 82 freshmen (students Faculty of Electrical Engineering (FEE) and Faculty of Mechanical Engineering (FMI)), out of those 47 belong to FEE.

To determine the level knowledge of physics at the beginning of the semester, after taking part in the course entitled The Introduction to Physics and after taking part in the course entitled Physics I, we used the standardized Force Concept Inventory (FCI) test [3]. The FCI test is mostly used conceptual test concerning introductory mechanics concepts. We used the FCI test to measure the effectiveness of teaching and development of the students'

conceptual understanding of introductory mechanics. The FCI is available online in many languages.

3 IPMACT AND EFFECTIVENESS

The FCI pre-test was attended by 82 students, the FCI post-test was attended by 38 students, subsequently, the paired test was done (36 freshmen of FEE and FMI). All the students taking part in the Summer Course increased their knowledge level. The average percentage of students' successfulness in the FCI pre-test was 26%, and the average percentage successfulness of 36 students in the FCI post-test after attending the Summer Course was 41%.

To enhance understanding of Newtonian mechanics, students were divided into two groups during their first semester. The control group had traditional lectures focus on quantitative calculations and analysis. The experimental group had interactive lectures which allowed students to model and analyse the motion of objects via videos using program Tracker. By overlaying simple dynamical models directly onto videos, students could see how well a model matches the real world which improved their qualitative understanding [was discussed in 4].

The FCI test was done by FEE freshmen during their first year of study. The pre-test was carried out at the beginning of the term during the first week (September 2016) and it was attended by 223 students (in Fig.4 N = number of students). The post-test was carried out at the end of the semester in the 13th week (December 2016) and it was attended by 207 students. This testing took place in the first semester. Subsequent testing after completing the course Physics I was completed at the end of the 13th week during the summer semester (May 2017) and it was attended by 133 students. Out of whom, some students were no longer in the study at the end of the second semester, some decided to start preparing for the entrance examination to medical universities (mainly biomedical engineering students), others decided to leave and go to work, some failed to complete the test because it was time-consuming (more as 30 minutes) and it was difficult for them to concentrate until the last 30th question.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of our research carried out previous years and at several faculties showed that the students' knowledge level has increased at the end of summer courses [4] as well as at the end of the first semester after attending interactive lectures [5 – at Faculty of Civil Engineering]. However, it should be noted that despite the increase of the knowledge level of our students, it still does not reach the input knowledge level of students studying at universities abroad and our freshmen even did not reach the minimal threshold (60% of the FCI test) so they are not able to understand Newtonian mechanics effectively [5, 6]. Therefore, it is necessary to think about the results and look for systematic solutions starting from secondary schools so the low prior knowledge of physics and mathematics was not the reason for drop out during the first semester.

Successfulness of students of FEE who participated in the Summer Course of Physics after first semester
 N = 47; M = 77.12; SD = 30.41; Max = 100%; Min = 0%

Fig. 1. Successfulness of students of FEE who participated in the Summer Course of Physics (Successfulness represents the percentage of the total number of credits gained during the first semester in terms of ECTS (30 credits = 100%)).

Successfulness of all enrolled students of FEE after first semester 2016/17
 N = 226; M = 75.32; SD = 31.42; Max = 100%; Min = 0%

Fig. 2. Successfulness of all enrolled students of FEE after first semester 2016/17

Next Fig. 1 shows the comparison of successfulness of freshmen who participated in the Summer Course of Physics in comparison with the successfulness of all enrolled students at FEE after first semester 2016/17 (Fig. 2). However, it is too early to state whether this tool is the appropriate one in terms of influencing students to continue in their study because the results presented in Fig. 1. and Fig. 2 are comparable. On the other hand, in combination with other interventions such as the attractiveness of interactive methods and formative feedback strategies, it may be one of the key tools. Based on the tables above, only 22% of students are at risk; however, the drop-out rate in academic years 2013/14, 2014/15, 2015/16 was about 33 – 47% [2].

Finally, Fig. 3 shows the successfulness of all students (185) at FEE after the first year 2016/17. The drop-out rate at FEE in 2016/17 after Summer Course of Physics, interactive Physics lectures using the video analysis and simulations (VAS) method of problem tasks) and their integration into STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) study programme and the implementation of intervention tools into our educational system (tutor, big brother/sister) was reduced to 24% at FEE.

As you can see in Fig. 3, 79% of students (green ones) do not need special attention. They are able to fulfil their duties. 7% of students (yellow ones) need to be *pushed* to study more, 4% of students (red ones) need our guidance and full attention. They need to be *caught by their hand* and led. 9% of students (grey ones) paid no attention to their studies and they did not even try to pass either their written or oral examination in order to gain their credits. (41 students (18%) prematurely failed to finish their studies during the 1st and 2nd semester.)

Fig. 3. Successfulness of all enrolled freshmen at FEE after first year of study 2016/17 (Successfulness represents the percentage of the total number of credits gained during the first year of study in terms of ECTS – 2 semesters (60 credits = 100%)).

4.1 Conception in Physics during the first year of study

We used a paired Student's t-test for further analysis. We used only answers of those students who took part in both pre- and post-tests plus answered all questions. As a result of pairing, the number of students was reduced to 100.

Average success rate (in Fig.4 M = mean) of 100 students in the FCI pre-test was 30.43%, and average success rate of students in the FCI post-test after attending The Introduction to Physics was 44.20% and after Physics I was 47.33%. What is surprising for us that the median in the FCI post-test after attending Physics is a little bit lower than after attending The Introduction to Physics I. Fig. 4 shows the FCI pre-test and post-test results.

Fig. 4. Numerical data for the histogram and boxplot

The evaluation of the post-tests and the pre-test at the beginning and end of the 1st and the 2nd semester (Fig. 4) confirmed the statistically significant difference between mean at the beginning and the end of the 1st semester ($P < 0.001$, $t_{\text{stat}} = 9.68 > t_{\text{critical}} = 1.98$) and between mean at the beginning and the end of the 2nd semester ($P < 0.01$, $t_{\text{stat}} = 2.78 > t_{\text{critical}} = 1.98$). (The post-test at the end of the 1st semester was considered the pre-test at the beginning of the 2nd semester).

Based on gained data we cannot state that the Summer course helped to eliminate the drop-out rate. The only thing we can prove is that the drop-out rate was reduced. We assume that the drop-out rate was reduced due to interactive lectures during the first year of study. In the future, we would like to find out the way how to verify the effectiveness of our interventions with regard to the drop-out rate; to be more specific, the focus will be placed on the Summer course.

5 SUMMARY

The common goal of the readySTEMgo project was to deliver the best scientist and engineers by providing a study environment that (1) optimally supports the development of STEM skills and (2) engages into learning outcomes that lead to high employment of future graduates [7, 8]. The main achievements of the readySTEMgo project were working on lowering the drop-out rate of freshmen, figuring out which intervention tools seem to be most appropriate and the implementation of intervention tools into our educational system.

Using the Summer Course of Physics, the Interactive Physics lectures using the video analysis and simulations (VAS) method of problem tasks and their integration into STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) study programme and the implementation of intervention tools into our educational system (tutor, big brother/sister) the drop-out rate was reduced to 24% at FEE after three years from starting implementing the readySTEMgo project.

By implementing this project, we have started an initiative to support mathematics and physics, worked on better guidance for students interested in the STEM study program. In future, we plan to continue organising the summer course of mathematics and physics, using interactive lectures and focusing on not only the cognitive skills but also the noncognitive skills of our students.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the by the Slovak Grant Agency KEGA through the projects No. 012TU Z-4/2017, No. 029ŽU-4/2018 and project Erasmus+: Strategic Partnership: Early identification of STEM readiness and targeted academic interventions (readySTEMgo): grant Decision number: 2014-BE02-KA200-000462. Authors would like to thank to David Koch from Arizona State University for providing the FCI.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pinxten, M, Hockicko, P. (2016), Predicting study success of first-year science and engineering students at the University of Žilina. Proc. of the 11th international Conference ELEKTRO 2016, Štrbské Pleso - High Tatras, May 16-18, proceedings: IEEE, ISBN 978-1-4673-8698-2. - CD-ROM, s. 18-23.

- [2] Hockicko, P., Tarjányiová, G. (2016), Force concept inventory of first year students attending Faculty of electrical engineering. Proc. of the 11th international Conference ELEKTRO 2016, Štrbské Pleso - High Tatras, May 16-18, 2016 Slovak Republic : proceedings: IEEE, 2016. - ISBN 978-1-4673-8698-2. - CD-ROM, s. 665-669.
- [3] Hestenes, D., Wells, M., Swackhamer, G. (1992), Force Concept Inventory, The Physics Teacher, Vol. 30, No. 3, pp. 141–158.
- [4] Hockicko, P., Tarjányiová, G., Sršňíková, D. (2017), The Effectiveness of Interactive Lectures on Students' Knowledge and Attitude to Further Study, Proceedings of the 45th SEFI Annual Conference 2017, 18 – 21 September 2017, Portugal, pp. 1045 - 1052, ISBN 978-989-98875-7-2
- [5] Hockicko, P., Krišťák, Ľ., Němec, M. (2014), Development of students' conceptual thinking by means of video analysis and interactive simulations at technical universities, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, vol. 40, iss 2, pp. 145 – 166.
- [6] Tiili, J., Hockicko, P., Suhonen, S., Tarjányiová, G., Ondruš, J. (2016), Ready to Study Engineering Physics in University? Comparison of mechanics skills between two European universities connected with engineering education. SEFI 2016 44th Annual Conference of European Society for Engineering Education, Tampere, Finland, 12 – 15 September 2016, Co-organised by SEFI and Tampere University of Technology, Brussels, Belgium (p.138), ISBN 978-2-87352-014-4
- [7] Pinxten M., Van Soom C., Peeters C., De Laet T., Pacher P., Hockicko and P., Langie G. (2016), Learning and study strategies of incoming science and engineering students. A comparative study between three institutions in Belgium, Slovakia, and Hungary. *Proceedings of the 44rd Annual SEFI Conference*. Annual Conference of European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI). Tampere (Finland), 12-15 September 2016.
- [8] Pinxten, M., Laet, T. De, Van Soon, C., Peeters, C., Kautz, C., Hockicko, P., Pacher, P, Nordstrom, K, Hawwash, K., Langie, G. (2017), Approaches to the Identification of STEM Key Competencies in European University systems, Proceedings of the 45th SEFI Annual Conference 2017, 18 – 21 September 2017, Portugal, pp. 389 -397.
- [9] Kopylova, N. (2018), The Use of E-Learning at Foreign Language Practical Lessons in a Technical University, Proceedings of 12th International Conference ELEKTRO 2018: Mikulov, Czech Republic, May 21-23, 2018, IEEE Catalog Number: CFP1848S-USB, 2018. ISBN 978-1-5386-4758-5, USB.
- [10] Tarjanyiova, G. Hockicko, P. (2018), The Importance of Physics Courses for Students of Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Proceedings of 12th International Conference ELEKTRO 2018: Mikulov, Czech Republic, May 21-23, 2018, IEEE Catalog Number: CFP1848S-USB, 2018. ISBN 978-1-5386-4758-5, USB.